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- 7, R=CH₃, R₁=CH₃, n=1 10; R=CH₃, R₁=SCH₃, n=2
 8; R=C₆H₅, R₁=CH₃, n=1 11; R=C₆H₅, R₁=SCH₃, n=2
 9, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=CH₃, n=1
 12, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=SCH₃, n=2

- 13, R=CH₃, R₁=R₂=H 16; R=CH₃, R₁=OH, R₂=CH₃
 14; R=C₆H₅, R₁=R₂=H 17; R=C₆H₅, R₁=OH, R₂=CH₃
 15, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=R₂=H
 18; R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=OH, R₂=CH₃

Synthesis of some Carboxyalkyl- and Pyrimidyl-substituted-thiocarbamides as Potential Fungicides and Nematicides

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SOME work has been reported on thiocarbamides and substituted-thiocarbamides with regards to their complexing ability, ionisation constants and fungicidal activities¹. The interest in the derivatives of thiocarbamides with heterodonor atoms with respect to their complexing ability, ionisation constants, fungicidal activity is of recent origin².

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. Isothiocyanates were prepared by usual methods³. The substituted-thiocarbamides, viz. *N*-methyl- (1), *N*-phenyl- (2) and *N*-allyl-*N'*-(1,5-dicarboxypropyl)thiocarbamide (3); *N*-methyl-(4), *N*-phenyl- (5) and *N*-allyl-*N'*-(1,4-dicarboxyethyl)-thiocarbamide (6); *N*-methyl- (7), *N*-phenyl- (8) and

- 1, R=CH₃, n=2 4, R=OH₂, n=1
 2, R=C₆H₅, n=2 5, R=C₆H₅, n=1
 3, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, n=2 6, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, n=1

N-allyl-*N'*-(carboxyethyl)thiocarbamide (9); bis-*N*-methyl- (10), bis-*N*-phenyl- (11) and bis-*N*-allyl-*N'*-(carboxyethylthio)thiocarbamide (12) were prepared as follows. A solution of the isothiocyanate (methyl, phenyl or allyl; 0.05 mol) was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol, and amino acid (glutamic acid, aspartic acid, alanine or cystine; 0.05 mol) in 1N NaOH (100 ml). Both the solutions were mixed and stirred at room temperature for 48 h. The solution was then filtered, cooled in an ice-bath and acidified with HCl (1:1). The resulting solid (substituted-thiocarbamide) was washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol.

N-Methyl- (13), *N*-phenyl- (14) and *N'*-allyl-*N'*-(2-pyrimidyl)thiocarbamide (15); *N*-methyl- (16), *N*-phenyl- (17) and *N*-allyl-*N'*-(4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidyl)thiocarbamide (18) were prepared as follows. To a solution of 2-aminopyrimidine (0.5 mol) in minimum quantity of ethanol, or to a solution of 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (0.5 mol) in minimum quantity of ethanol-water mixture 50% (v/v), an equal amount of the isothiocyanate (methyl, phenyl or allyl) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h and cooled when crystals of substituted-pyrimidylthiocarbamides separated out which were recrystallised from ethanol. Uv spectra (EtOH) of the thiocarbamides were taken on a UV-VIS PMQ3 spectrophotometer. The transition energy (*E*_T) and molar extinction coefficient *ε*_{max} were calculated by using standard equations. *R*_T values of the thiocarbamides in ethyl acetate-benzene and ethyl acetate-carbon tetrachloride were calculated (Table 1). Ir spectra (nujol/KBr) of these thiocarbamides were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The carboxyalkyl-substituted-thiocarbamides show absorption maxima at 200-210 and 260-275

NOTES

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE THIOCARBAMIDES (1–18)

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	Mol. wt.	M.p. °C	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\epsilon_{\max}$ dm ² mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	E_T kJ mol ⁻¹	R_f values	
							EtOAc + C ₆ H ₆ (1 : 4)	EtOAc + COI ₄ (1 : 1)
1	C ₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S	220	196	201	9 904	595.09	0.880	0.916
				242	18 934	494.30		
				264	27 520	453.09		
2	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	282	140	201	9 801	595.09	0.829	0.918
				238	18 449	502.58		
				265	28 330	451.37		
3	C ₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	246	162	198	10 416	604.13	0.826	0.919
				238	19 452	502.58		
				265	27 457	451.37		
4	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	206	205	202	10 275	592.16	0.872	0.881
				236	20 083	506.85		
				264	26 711	453.09		
5	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ S	268	175	202	9 925	592.16	0.669	0.696
				236	18 320	506.85		
				264	28 340	453.09		
6	C ₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	232	186	199	10 491	601.07	0.670	0.686
				241	20 603	496.35		
				265	29 430	451.37		
7	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	162	190	204	10 671	586.35	0.710	0.713
				246	17 622	486.22		
				272	28 141	439.78		
8	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S	224	192	202	11 516	593.42	0.713	0.716
				245	18 121	488.23		
				271	28 820	441.37		
9	C ₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S	188	202	203	12 110	589.23	0.714	0.718
				245	18 822	488.23		
				270	29 120	443.00		
10	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	386	200	204	11 371	586.35	0.861	0.863
				245	19 526	388.23		
				270	27 391	443.00		
11	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	510	180	203	12 191	589.23	0.841	0.852
				243	18 661	492.25		
				270	26 503	443.00		
12	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	438	190	202	11 841	593.42	0.820	0.884
				243	18 211	492.25		
				270	25 222	443.00		
13	C ₆ H ₉ N ₄ S	168	86	205	9 745	583.50	0.623	0.626
				235	17 310	508.98		
				295	22 212	405.47		
14	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	280	76	204	9 817	586.35	0.620	0.628
				286	18 720	506.83		
				295	23 420	405.47		
15	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	194	105	205	10 620	583.50	0.619	0.624
				237	19 294	504.72		
				296	24 697	404.09		
16	C ₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS	198	246	205	10 810	583.50	0.858	0.871
				238	19 916	502.58		
				285	24 310	419.70		
17	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₄ OS	280	221	204	10 760	586.39	0.861	0.866
				239	19 116	500.49		
				286	25 460	418.23		
18	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS	224	230	202	12 229	593.42	0.824	0.829
				240	19 407	498.40		
				284	25 220	421.16		

nm which may be due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of C=O, and at 240–250 nm may be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ thiocarbonyl transition. In pyrimidyl thiocarbamides, a maxima at 201–207, 280–295 and 230–240 nm may be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (high energy)

pyrimidyl, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ pyrimidyl and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ thiocarbonyl transitions⁴, respectively.

In the infrared spectra of the substituted-thiocarbamides, a single unsymmetrical peak at 3 300–3 350 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{OH}+\text{NH}}$ ⁵, a weak band at 3 020–

3 070 cm^{-1} due to 2-aminopyrimidyl mode⁶ and a strong band at 1 630–1 655 cm^{-1} due to $\delta_{\text{NH}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ ⁷ have been observed. These bands suggest the presence of pyrimidine ring in the compounds. A weak band at 1 500–1 530 cm^{-1} assigned to $\text{NH} + (\text{C}=\text{S}) + \text{NCS}$ deformation, a weak band at 1 410–1 435 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{NH}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}} + \nu_{\text{NCN}}$, a weak band at 1 300–1 320 cm^{-1} assigned to $\delta_s(\text{NH} + \text{CH}_3)$ mode⁷, a medium intensity band at 1 200–1 270 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}} + \nu_{\text{NCN}}$ have been observed. A peak of medium intensity at 1 015–1 050 cm^{-1} has been assigned to the vibrational (N–C–N–rock) + (N–C–N + C=S)⁸ and an intense band at 700–720 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}} + \nu_{\text{NCS}}$ ⁹. A strong band at 600–650 cm^{-1} assigned to δ_{CH} ⁸, a strong band at 530–560 cm^{-1} assigned to δ_{NCS} and a band of moderate intensity at 420–460 cm^{-1} assigned to NCS bending have been observed. All these peaks suggest the most probable structures of the thiocarbamides.

Antifungal activity: Antifungal activity of the compounds was tested by standard spore germination inhibition method¹⁰ against two fungi *Colletotrichum falcatum* and *Alternaria brassicae* causing major diseases of sugarcane and *Brassica* group of crops, respectively. It was observed that compounds 6–9, 12, 13, 15–18 were highly toxic against *C. falcatum* and compounds 13, 15–18 were toxic against *A. brassicae*.

Nematicidal activity: Nematicidal activity of the compounds was tested at different dilutions against two important nematode pests *Meloidogyne javanica* and *Anguina tritici*. Observations on mortality were recorded by counting the living and dead second stage larvae under stereoscopic microscope. Compounds 2, 9, 13, 16–18 were highly effective against *M. javanica* and compounds 1, 7, 8 and 14 were effective against *A. tritici*.

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Preparation of 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-Thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(substituted-phenylthioureido)-s-triazine and Study of their Antibacterial Activity

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SEVERAL related 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(substituted-phenylthioureido)-s-triazine (1), where the substitution R = phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-nitrophenyl, *m*-nitrophenyl, *p*-nitrophenyl, *o*-chlorophenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, have been prepared in view of the fact that a number of related compounds are known to have biological activities¹.

N¹-2-Thiazolylsulphanilamide was condensed with cyanuric chloride to give 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4,6-dichloro *s*-triazine, which when condensed with *p*-bromoaniline gave 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolylsulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine, and the latter on reaction with various phenylthioureas yield the compound of the type (1).

Experimental

Infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-N⁴-{N¹-(2'-Thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine : N¹-2-Thiazolylsulphanilamide (0.05 mol, 12.75 g) dissolved in acetone was added in a well stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.05